

Ref. Ares (2023)7371660 - 30/10/2023
Grant Agreement Number: 101132538; Project Acronym: STRATEGIES;
Project Full Title: SUSTAINABLE TRANSITION FOR EUROPE'S GAME INDUSTRIES

STRATEGIES

Sustainable Transition
for Europe's Game Industries

Design Pattern Research and its Applicability to Ecogame Design

Actual Delivery Date: May 6, 2026

Lead participant: Stefan Werning

Dissemination level: public

This project has received funding from the UK Research and Innovation Horizon Guarantee Programme and from the European Union's Horizon Research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101132538.

Document Control Sheet

Deliverable Number	n/a
Deliverable Responsible	n/a
Work Package	WP5
Editor	Stefan Werning

Author(s) – in alphabetical order		
Name	Organisation	Email
Stefan Werning	Utrecht University	s.werning@uu.nl

Document Revision History			
Version	Date	Comments	Modified by
1.1	April 6, 2026	First complete draft	Stefan Werning
1.5	May 6, 2026	Revised and extended version connecting to ecogame design research within STRATEGIES, particularly the Green Mediography	Stefan Werning

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1 Introduction

This report outlines existing research on design patterns relevant for ecogame design and briefly discusses their applicability within the Design Pattern Library and for the purposes of the STRATEGIES project. The 'design pattern' concept, often attributed to Christopher Alexander's work on landscape design from the late 1970s (Hansen 2024), has been used in a variety of academic and design contexts to introduce shared vocabulary and to acknowledge how recurring patterns, archetypes and solutions to common problems/challenges shape the designer's imagination.

It has been adapted to games by Bjork, Holopainen and Lundgren (2003) in the early consolidation period of game studies as a discipline to inform contemporary game analysis methodologies. **Design patterns are usually described in a semi-formalized manner**, although not all categories are always present. Apart from the title and a short description, examples from existing games are referenced for illustration purposes. Usually, the 'implementation' is discussed e.g. in terms of how the pattern relies on or clashes with specific mechanics or dynamics as defined by the MDA framework (Hunicke et al. 2004). Finally, (both positive and negative) relationships with other patterns are similarly addressed.

1.1 DEFINING (GAME) DESIGN PATTERNS

Two characteristic elements of (game) design patterns, compared e.g. to mechanics or genre elements, is a) their function as **reusable solution templates for recurring design problems** and b) the **focus on relationships to other design patterns**, which – in Christopher Alexander's terminology – leads to a 'pattern language'. On that note, (Bjork et al. 2003) argue that, "unlike most design patterns", they chose "not to define [game design] patterns as a pure problem-solution pairs" (185). This is to avoid framing "patterns as a tool for problem-solving only and not as a tool to support creative design work" and because of redundancies in the patterns they identified. The categories they suggest are "Name", "**Description**", "**Consequences**", "**Using the Pattern**", and "**Relations**" (185), which are expressed primarily hierarchically as "**Subpatterns & Superior Patterns**" (189). However, in practice this leads to 'patterns' that appear quite generic like e.g. "Secret Tactics", "Game Mastery" or "Character Development" (which is complemented by the fact that this study does not focus on particularly game genres, themes or purposes). Thus, the problem focus appears useful to retain as long as it is not applied 'mechanistically' as the term "problem-solution pairs" used by the authors implies. Generally, the tension between specificity and generalizability remains a constant theme in game design pattern literature.

To complement these basic categories, Argasiński and Węgrzyn (2019) suggest including „**evidence**“, i.e. one-sentence descriptions of how the player successfully engages with a pattern, and „**affect**“ (533), i.e. the expected emotional impact of these actions, in the description of design patterns for serious games. A downside of this study is the focus on quantifiability (e.g. as „weak“, „medium“ or „strong“) as well as „detect[ability]“ (534), which appears too schematic and inflexible for the case at hand. In comparison, it might be more productive to utilize established emotional taxonomies, specifically those related to the global climate crisis (e.g. Pihkala 2022). Emotional taxonomies can also help identify hybrid areas of

emotional response, e.g. ecological melancholy blending aspects of the 'basic' emotions of fear (or, more mildly, apprehension) and sadness. These affective or emotional implications may taper off but also compound through repeated activation dependent on the player and play situation, which has both positive and negative implications.

Eriksson et al. (2019) identify **four distinct purposes of design patterns in the context of serious games**; these include a) „problem-solving for game interaction design“, b) „inspiration“ in collaborative design contexts, c) acting as a „structured design tool“ that condense complex ideas into reusable patterns and relationships between patterns, and d) as a means of focused „communication“ between different stakeholders (p. 16). All four functions directly apply to the STRATEGIES project as the design pattern library is intended to broaden ecogame rhetorics and aesthetics by facilitating dialogue between academic disciplines, industry partners and societal institutions. Below, specific design patterns derived and adapted from the literature will be marked in **bold type** for easy identifiability.

1.2 AN EXAMPLE: DESIGNING FOR EMOTION IN EDUCATION

While not limited to ecogames, design patterns about “how **emotions** are embedded in games and how games sustain **affective learning**” (Dormann et al. 2013) can be a useful starting point. The authors report on dedicated techniques for “the design of affective learning and encourage more games that enroll emotions into their design” (216).

Sample patterns for that purpose include...

- „**Avatar Emotional Expression**” (219) [player character facially reacting to in-game behavior],
- **NPCs With Emotional Masks** (221) [NPCs hiding their 'real', i.e. intended emotions],
- **Avatar Display of Human Frailty** (221) [player character exhibits bodily limitations],
- the “**Traumatized Avatar**” [player character reflecting psychological impact of in-game behavior],
- “**Healing/Nurturing Others**”,
- “**Animal Companion Sims**” (225) [“reproduce[ing] the effects of actual pet ownership”],
- “**Emotional Decision Making**” (227) [player choices aim for specific emotional response],
- **Consequences of Long Ago Actions**, [and]
- **Empowerment.**“

These design patterns comprise a broad range of engagement strategies but also focus on the use of non-player characters (NPCs) as well as the malleability of the player character (or “avatar”), which a) would need to be adapted to analogue game design contexts and b) may limit inclusivity since the design and appeal of fictional characters is highly subjective and may easily deter players due to a lack of relatability. **Emotional Decision Making** and especially **Empowerment** are promising and both can be connected with the more specific patterns outlined below to maximize their impact. Below, the potential usefulness of these and other previously identified game design patterns is assessed by emulating a specific use case, i.e. a hypothetical game project about sustainable energy futures.

2 Patterns in Climate Communication Games

Despite the current deluge of climate- and nature-themed commercial games, both in the digital and analogue game industries, there is little published research yet about how to systematically design for effective climate communication and education using a concept like design patterns. Instead, most studies (for example, consider chapters on games like *Fate of the World*, *Kentucky Route Zero* or *Metro: Exodus* from Beke et al. 2024) focus on 1-2 case studies and inductively identify (sometimes generalizable) design heuristics specific to these games.

In comparison, Whittle et al. (2022) report on the work of the International Game Developers Association (IGDA) on designing games for sustainability awareness, which yields several 'design patterns' specific to climate communication (though not explicitly using the term and concept). The following design considerations may inspire game design patterns though, importantly, they are not deliberately formulated to address specific problems and operate on a higher level of abstraction than traditional design patterns, which makes them more difficult to adapt to specific game or mod contexts:

- **Abstraction**, i.e. „break[ing] down highly complex situations into simplified, more abstract terms“ (26), possibly using fantasy settings or concepts as metaphors to „sidestep barriers preventing players from forming pro-environmental attitudes“ (27). Still, since many ecogames foreground a specific setting, fantastical elements are not always applicable, but abstraction can still be relevant e.g. to convey complex issues like, in the context of the energy transition, the implications of peak shaving on a national level or the possibility of transitioning to alternative energy sources and storage solutions.
- **Intrinsic integration**, which „means that content knowledge is critical to every interaction of the game system“ (28), i.e. real-world knowledge is useful in the game rather than including too many arbitrary gameplay elements (e.g. puzzles, platforming etc.) to make interaction more fun.
- **Forced Discomfort**, which puts players „into physical or psychological situations that can create unease, annoyance, or anxiety“ (31) to emphasize otherwise currently ‚intangible‘ problems, e.g. social injustice issues or intensifying future collateral events in case the energy crisis does not progress in time. This can be a powerful tool but its impact differs notably between so-called ‚serious‘ and commercial games (which are individually purchased primarily as entertainment products) and it should be approached cautiously to avoid creating the impression that there are no viable solutions, which can easily foster apathy.
- **Conflicting Goals**, „which force the player into a situation requiring a delicate balance between choices.“ (47) This can teach players to accept and valorize imperfect successes where necessary but also to use resources as efficiently as possible to at least partially satisfy all requirements. An obvious trade-off in an energy game context would be balancing a household's sustainable choices and financial well-being but maybe also social expectations (e.g. a child wanting a game console, which consumes a lot of energy but also facilitates socializing with their peers).

However, design patterns are not only useful as archetypes to collaboratively plan and streamline design processes but can also be *used to analyze existing (game) designs*, especially in a bigger corpus of games on the same general subject matter, as Barnes et al. (2017) show with their analysis of „student-made climate change games“ (1). The authors do not use the design patterns concept very rigidly but differentiate between recurring themes (like veganism or deforestation) and popular game genres. However, this approach can be usefully adapted to the evaluation of ecogame design workshops; comparing design

suggestions against the design pattern library allows for grouping similar ideas but also translating them into actionable design suggestions.

While research on design patterns specifically for ecogames is not currently available (but will result from the design pattern library developed by the STRATEGIES project), one potential reference point besides the aforementioned IGDA resource may be a recent study on “gamification design patterns” for “sustainability-oriented innovation challenges” (Breuer and Ivanov 2026), though it focuses specifically on “organisational challenges” (154) in larger companies or similar institutions and the identified patterns are, consequently, quite broad and not particularly tailored to the challenges of (even intra-organizational) climate communication. Patterns are grouped by “thematic areas of innovation management challenges” (159) and comprise a) flow patterns, i.e. “reusable flows of interactions between participants and artefacts to address an innovation challenge” and a larger number of subordinate “gamification component patterns” (both 158). Flow patterns include “Agile Retrospective, Awareness Raising, Business Modelling, Business Simulation, Dilemma Solving, Gamified Crowdsourcing, Experiential Learning, Ideation, Innovation Markets, Warm- Ups and Workshop Facilitation” while component patterns include “Branching Choices, Cards, Challenges, Collective Decisions, Competition, Cooperation, Day in the Life, Dedicated Facilitators, Epic Meaning, Humour, Mapping, Metaphors, Modelling Materials, Mutual Goals, Negotiation, Pitch, Prioritisation, Quizzes, Resources, Rewards, Roles, Storytelling, Surprise, Trade- offs and Voting” (all 160). The study does list related patterns for each entry, thereby providing a framework for a ‘pattern language’, and the listed patterns provide a valuable glimpse at how organizations internally conceptualize sustainability challenges (as well as the rather narrow concept of ‘games’ or ‘gamification’ used to address them); however, as inspiration for ecogame design they are only relevant on a very basic level.

3 Patterns for Social Interaction

Design patterns addressing social interaction between players primarily address collaborative behavior, which appears directly relevant for ecogame design. Bunker et al. (2017) emphasize the *importance of collaborative design patterns* as opposed to the focus on competition that still, though increasingly less so, characterizes many commercially successful games, particularly in analogue gaming. The authors differentiate between “cooperative games”, which John Nash describes more neutrally as “situations involving two individuals whose interests are neither completely opposed nor completely coincidental”, but which encourage “discuss[ing] the situation, and agree[ing] on a rational joint plan of action”, and „collaborative games“ in which according to Jose Zagal „all the participants work together as a team, sharing the payoffs and outcomes“ (1).

Based on previous research, several recurring patterns were identified; the ones with particular relevance for ecogame design are listed below:

- **Complementarity**, which involves players using character roles that complement each other. See e.g. *Lego Marvel Superheroes (Traveller's Tales, 2013)*
- **Synergy between abilities**, where one character can change or assist the abilities of another. See e.g. *World of Warcraft (Blizzard, 2004)*

- **Abilities that can only be used on another player**, which involves restricting player abilities like healing or shielding so they do not work on the activating player.
See e.g. *Team Fortress 2* (Valve, 2007)
- **Shared goals**, where a group of players are given a single quest with a shared objective.
See e.g. *MMOs like World of Warcraft*
- **Synergies between goals**, which encourages players to cooperate by assigning them mutually beneficial goals. See e.g. *Team Fortress 2*
- **Special rules**, that can alter how certain actions affect cooperating players (like friendly fire or AOE healing).
- **Interacting with the same object**, i.e. objects that players can all manipulate or might even only be able to manipulate collectively. See e.g. *Beautiful Katamari* (Namco Bandai, 2007)
- **Shared puzzles**, i.e. puzzles and general gameplay situation that require players to work together to solve/overcome. See e.g. *Lego Marvel Superheroes*
- **Limited resources**, which requires players to share resources like money, regenerative items or ammunition. *Borderlands* (Gearbox, 2009).

Two game-specific patterns were found that can be interpreted more broadly to inspire relevant design choices for ecogames.

- **Special characters targeting a lone wolf**, is a pattern that involves non-player characters (NPCs) targeting players that work alone. *Left4Dead* (Valve, 2008).
This can be interpreted as „rules that temporarily disadvantage players not participating in social features or the aforementioned collaborative design patterns.
- **Vocalization**, where characters indicate the occurrence of events (for example objectives, or the arrival of tough enemies) through voice or text.
This could be interpreted as functions that let players provide helpful information to others, possibly under specific conditions like ‘limited communication’ in board/card game contexts.

Some of these patterns are easier to combine than others. For example, **limited resources**, **complementarity**, and **interaction with the same object** were defined as being “closely-coupled”, while **shared puzzles**, **abilities that can be used on other players**, and **shared goals** are more “loosely-coupled” (3). A later study by Reuter et al. (2014) builds on these taxonomies, adding further patterns that partially overlap with but also complement the aforementioned examples.

- **„Concurrency“**, which is described as „operating one or more objects simultaneously that could not be operated by a single player alone“ (7). This could e.g. refer to sustainable upgrades that need to be purchased and/or operated together by more than one player.
- **„Parallelization“** (8), i.e., „splitting work that could be done alone in order to speed it up or to make it easier.“ This could also include pooling resources (i.e. splitting the acquisition of resources) for specific tasks.
- **„Separation gate“** (9), which in commercial games literally „forc[es] the players to split up by allowing only a certain number of players to continue“. Temporarily taking away social interaction and mutual support can make it appear even more relevant once it is made available again later on.

- „Resupply“ (10), which lets one player „restore a positive capability for another player,“ along with related patterns like „Protector“ and „Savior“ (11), which allow players to mitigate negative effects on others, potentially requiring a „Sacrifice“ (12), e.g. having to give up money, items or one's own actions as a consequence.

A study on design patterns in games for children (Eriksson et al. 2019) similarly focuses a lot on collaboration-oriented patterns, specifically to create a more inclusive experience e.g. for children with intellectual disabilities or social anxieties. Patterns like „togetherness“, i.e. experiencing (virtual) co-presence, „collaborative actions“ and „mutual goals“ were found to be particularly helpful to encourage different types of children to participate (19). However, the study also references potentially detrimental patterns in collaborative games like „alpha player“, which refers to how more experienced players can sometimes ‚dictate‘ how others should play to achieve the best results (which can compromise the group identity collaborative situation), and „downtime“, i.e. having to wait for other players' input before being able to continue with a specific action in-game (both 19). An interesting pattern that is – however – only addressed in passing by the authors is „shared rewards“ (20), which both visualizes the shared achievement and might be further experimented with, e.g. by accentuating generosity and gift economy principles, which are sometimes referenced as part of eco literacy frameworks (see e.g. McBride et al. 2013), which outline principles of sustainable future communities and are therefore vital for the energy transition as an effective and just sociotechnical process.

Finally, social interaction is also addressed in the climate game design patterns of the IGDA, though in more generic terms, e.g. through the patterns **Collaboration** (67), **Competition** (69), and **Facilitation** (70). The authors acknowledge that “competition over who can extract non-renewable resources the fastest encourages players to adopt a ‘me first’ attitude” (69), which seems undesirable in many ecogame contexts and the real-world systems they symbolically represent. However, if the game showed the limits of competition (e.g. by making the contested resources particularly scarce) and offered (or at least hinted at) collaborative alternatives, this limitation might be turned into an advantage. **Facilitation** refers to how a game can spark conversation while and/or after playing; while many collaborative games benefit from this kind of exchange, it does not emerge automatically but can be catalysed through thoughtful, even sometimes small design choices. For example, if players in a card game may not simply show their cards to others, this can already incentivize them to actively share information with others and, in the process, coordinate their actions. Some of the aforementioned patterns like **Complementarity** are also suitable for this purpose, as – in this case – complementary advantages or disadvantages require players to repeatedly coordinate their efforts, strategies and tactics, potentially drawing on real-world experience in the process.

4 Patterns for Specific Literacies

Apart from general patterns of interaction like collaboration and competition, design patterns can also inform the creation of serious games for particular knowledge domains and skills, which are often summarized using specific literacy frameworks. For example, Werning (2020) uses the notion of (creative) data literacy to guide and evaluation game co-design workshops with students, breaking down the rather elusive concept into more specific and (at least tentatively) measurable skills like ‘arguing with data’ or understanding the role of tools in standardizing our interpretation of data. Another study by Paeßens and

Winther (2021) explores design patterns based on a game that specifically teaches financial literacy. Both skillsets are not specific to sustainable futures but are becoming increasingly important also for individuals and households because of „economic and financial crises taking place at the macro-level“, and „high per capita indebtedness of private households, precarious employment, complex financial services, and the need for private provision [...] at the micro-level“ (44). For example, financial literacy is an important framework for participating in sustainable developments like the energy transition, since consumer choices often depend on financial means and new technologies often incur at least high short-term costs that create potential additional inequalities.

The authors mention several broader design patterns that can make game-based learning inclusive, e.g. „**discover the fun of learning**“, „**receiving suggestions for everyday life and work**“, and „**reaching other groups of learners**“. However, the design patterns the authors propose based on their sample game are rather generic and, thus, only applicable for more abstract design considerations. Useful examples include „**modularity**“, „**openness and flexibility**“, „**competence orientation**“ (i.e. being „built on a systematic competence model“), and „**learner orientation**“ (i.e. connecting with „realistic experiences“ identifiable by the target audience to make the game more relatable) (48). The focus on realistic experience particularly applies e.g. to co-design or modding contexts, as this often allows for players to tailor a game's design to their idiosyncratic experience.

An important lacuna in the current research on game design patterns for the STRATEGIES project would be design patterns aimed at promoting frameworks like *energy literacy*. While there are no published studies to directly draw from, existing literature using energy literacy in relation to game design (see e.g. Bayley et al. 2020) can provide valuable inspiration. An application-oriented taxonomy of energy literacy elements could be mapped onto the aforementioned design patterns and design choices from commercial games to derive usable design guidelines.

For example, Bayley et al. (2020) highlight children as a target audience as they „are the decision makers of the future“, yet currently „under-represented in studies aiming to affect householders' energy literacy“ (531). The concept is rather loosely defined as possessing „knowledge which empowers [children] to make informed rational energy decisions and actions“. The authors further emphasize „the connection between energy use, its potential sources, and the environmental consequences of its misuse“ as a particularly important but difficult-to-convey topic. Moreover, discussions at home usually foreground „saving costs rather than saving the environment“, i.e. a balance between different social needs must be taken into account as well. The sample game, aimed at „5-9 year olds“, involves „collecting tokens by jumping onto roofs and buildings to switch off lights; activating solar panels at the top of buildings to save the town energy; pushing boxes to prevent heat leaking from buildings; swinging from clouds to release rainwater to grow young saplings, and turning of steam taps in the underground coal plant to save water and power.“ (532) A useful design choice seems to be the persistent use of kilowatt hours (kWh) as a metric. While this is not discussed further in the text, this may gradually familiarize children with the respective costs but also saving potentials of different activities through repeated exposure. Furthermore, given the aforementioned focus on affective aspects of design patterns (Argasiński and Węgrzyn 2019), this may also give younger children a sense of mastery and empowerment in using this metric as a way to see and interpret their world.

5 Towards a Framework for Ecogame Analysis

More than 20 years after its first wave of adoption in game studies, the design pattern concept is actively used to this day, though the corresponding areas of applications are often very specific (for example using patterns to design 'poetic gameplay'; see Mitchell et al. 2024) and despite the alleged modularity of design patterns as a concept, there are few attempts to use these individual pattern libraries in conjunction (as this white paper has tentatively done). This concluding chapter thus offers suggestions on how to extend the aforementioned design patterns into a more holistic framework for ecogame analysis.

5.1 BEYOND (ECO)GAME DESIGN PATTERNS

While formulating the ecogame design pattern library for the STRATEGIES project, it thus appears imperative to cast the net wide and to also incorporate and adapt findings from related studies and design contexts, e.g. on sustainability-oriented design patterns in non-game contexts. For example, Lockton et al. (2013) utilize the design pattern approach as part of a "toolkit for [sustainable] behaviour change" (3), which focuses on the design of everyday objects and environments. This includes usage scenarios like closing curtains to reduce reliance on heating or turning off the tap while brushing one's teeth. However, among other 'lenses' or categories of patterns, it also includes a "**ludic lens**", referring to "techniques for influencing user behaviour that can be derived from games and other 'playful' interactions" (4) and the study focuses on how designers use these patterns to generate design/product concepts but also on how the patterns informed "how participants considered the roots of the problems differently" (8). Other relevant lenses from the same study include "**architectural**" elements [based on "environmental design"], "**errorproofing**" [framing unsustainable behavior as an 'error' that design should help users avoid or remedy], "**interaction**" [interaction design and persuasive technology features], "**perceptual**" elements [focusing primarily on visual but possibly also other sensory modes of perception], "**cognitive**" elements [leveraging users' biases, cultural assumptions and decision-making heuristics] and "**Machiavellian**" elements [i.e. design patterns that follow an "'end justifies the means'" approach] (4). While the resulting list of design patterns is not specifically tailored to games, these pattern 'categories' can be very useful as context for working with the STRATEGIES design pattern library.

5.2 VALIDATING (ECO)GAME DESIGN PATTERNS

Another important consideration for future research involves assessing the impact of design patterns. For example, earlier studies summarized by Bunker et al. (2017) suggested several **criteria to evaluate design patterns** (in this case combinations of "cooperative design patterns to improve player experience"), which include a) laughter or excitement together, b) observable instances of „strategies, when players discussed a problem aloud“, c) occurrences of helping each other, d) observable instances of „global strategies“ (i.e. thinking as a group), e) occurrences where players „waited for each other“, and – as a negative metric – f) occurrences where players „got in each other's way“ (2). The authors refer to behavioural studies that provide anecdotal evidence, e.g. tested by having focus groups respond to social dilemma situations after playing a game, of how „participants who played cooperatively were more generous“ (3) than those playing a competitive version of the same game. Thus, specific forms of post-tests can be designed to tentatively

assess the (short- to mid-term) impact of design patterns, especially if versions without the pattern(s) or using different patterns can be produced for a control group. To conclude, this focus on assessment criteria and formats constitutes one of the most important directions for evidence-based research on (eco)game design patterns moving forward, not least to validate the ongoing usefulness of the concept itself.

5.3 A PLATFORM FOR ECOGAME DESIGN PATTERNS: THE GREEN MADIOGRAPHY

To work as a formal 'language', design patterns need to be actively used and discussed, individually and in relation to each other. Therefore, general-purpose design pattern approaches have usually sought to establish (online) platforms to facilitate that discussion. Examples include e.g. earlier initiatives like the *Game Ontology* project¹, which emerged shortly after the early wave of scholarly interest in formal game analysis (going back to studies like Bjork et al. 2003) but also more recent endeavours like industry veteran Christopher Barney's *Design Pattern Library*² accompanying his more recent book on game design patterns (Barney 2021).

Similarly, the STRATEGIES project is embedded its emerging design pattern library for ecogame design within an online platform, the *Green Mediography*, which allows for combining the patterns with sample game analyses (analogue, digital and multimodal) as well as related literature. For that purpose, we developed a comprehensive taxonomy that both applies to game examples and design patterns and provides semantic context for 'formal language' constituted by the design patterns. For example, design patterns with the tag 'ecological identity' (Light 2000) are, through the tag, linked to games addressing the same concept. Through other shared tags, these patterns are conceptually linked to other design patterns, thus forming a 'pattern language' that is enacted through repeated use³. To explain how to use the design pattern library within the Green Mediography, the shared taxonomies will be briefly explained and motivated below.

Apart from other metadata like the associated sustainable development goals (SDGs), the project relies on three taxonomies, i.e. **genre tags**, relying on game genre theory (Clarke et al. 2015) but also emerging classification terminology like 'souls-likes' or 'auto-battlers', **motif tags**, focusing on themes, rhetorical, cultural or socio-technical aspects, and **affective tags**, which specifically highlight emotional responses that the games in question may elicit or enable players to engage with. Importantly, the latter two taxonomies – which are specific to how these games frame the climate crisis and sustainable futures – also include ambivalent or negative descriptors, e.g. 'frictionless restoration' in the motif category or 'emotional desensitization' in the affective category, both in relation to the games and design patterns. Thereby, **the platform does not categorically distinguish between positive design patterns and "anti-patterns"** (Widdicks et al. 2020), i.e. unhelpful or even damaging design practices established over time. Instead, productive and problematic design elements are combined into a taxonomy, which reflects the broad range of potential benefits but also misconceptions players may derive from a game depending on the play situation and their own disposition.

¹ See https://gameontology.com/index.php/Main_Page.

² See <https://patternlanguageforgamedesign.com/PatternLibraryApp/>.

³ In traditional pattern taxonomies, these relationships are, if they exist at all, often 'hard-coded' through a field listing 'related patterns' or 'mutually exclusive patterns'.

It also reflects the fact that the term ‘ecogames’, though widely used by now, is still not conclusively defined (op de Beke et al. 2024). For example, while some use the term primarily with reference to games that thematize individual experiences of nature and motifs like regeneration, others apply it primarily to games that are explicitly political and critique the politico-institutional frameworks that enabled the climate crisis and allow it to exacerbate. While an ‘authoritative’ definition is unrealistic, both practically and conceptually, the interrelated tags used by the Green Mediography to categorize design patterns and game examples provide much-needed concreteness but also retain the necessary flexibility to avoid pigeonholing the ‘ecogame’ label.

For example, **environmental, ecological and eco-literacy** (see e.g. McBride et al. 2013) are important foundational tags that define specific skills and knowledge areas that a game may contribute to (positively or negatively for that matter, e.g. in the case of games with the aforementioned ‘frictionless restoration’ tag, that portray environmental cleanup as quick and non-residual). Another tag that broadens the spectrum of ‘ecogames’ is ‘**ecological identity**’ (see e.g. Light 2000), which refers to design patterns that enable players to incorporate aspects of sustainability, degrowth, climate justice, conservationism and related topics into the way they construct and perform their own identity in everyday life. Tags referring to specific **climate emotions** (see e.g. Pihkala 2022) such as climate anxiety but also more specific experiences like solastalgia or a sense of ecological stewardship further broad the scope as even games without an explicit nature/climate focus can help players negotiate or cultivate these emotions. Moreover, tags like ‘**crisis of imagination**’ (see e.g. Hajer and Oomen 2025) designate games that outline new as well as concretize, stabilize or challenge existing sustainable future imaginaries, i.e. “script[s]” (4-5) for alternative social, economic and/or political systems that promise to help mitigate the damage and injustice caused by the ongoing climate crisis. Most tags that go beyond literal themes (like food security or renewable energy) are similarly derived from climate communication and ecomedia studies. For example, the tag ‘**bad environmentalism**’, by which Nicole Seymour refers to ecomedia that utilize “irreverent affects” (Seymour 2018) often considered inappropriate in climate communication like playfulness, glee or sardonic humour, can be used to highlight characteristic design elements such as mocking the cult-like aspects of recycling through the figure of the “recyclepath” in the game *Omori*⁴. While *Omori* itself would not usually be characterized as an ‘ecogame’, this particular design element is very productive – not to discourage but to rethink ‘green practices’ such as recycling – and can be abstracted into a design pattern to address common challenges such as reaching audiences disillusioned by or even rejecting the often inherently persuasive representations of recycling and similar ‘sustainable behaviours’ (see e.g. Lockton et al. 2013) in games and other media.

To conclude, by combining the design pattern library with 200+ samples analyses using the aforementioned taxonomy as a conceptual link, the *Green Mediography* positions itself as a framework for ecogame analysis that facilitates a productive collaboration between game industry practitioners, academics and other societal actors utilizing ecogames like educators, journalists or NGOs. As of May 2026, the platform is still in development but is being tentatively used and extended by STRATEGIES researchers and industry partners. We are also in discussion with the Climate special interest group (SIG) of the International Game Developers Association (IGDA) on cross linking between their online ecogame library *GreenGameDesign*⁵

⁴ See e.g. <https://omori.fandom.com/wiki/RECYCLEPATH>.

⁵ See <https://www.greengamedesign.com/>.

and the *Green Mediography* to intensify the collaboration between game designers, developers and scholars and support the role of games as a potential catalyst for climate action and sustainable development.

Works Cited

- Argasiński, Jan K., and Paweł Węgrzyn. 2019. 'Affective Patterns in Serious Games'. *Future Generation Computer Systems* 92 (March): 526–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2018.06.013>.
- Barnes, Jackie, Amy K. Hoover, Borna Fatehi, Jesús Moreno-León, Gillian Smith, and Casper Harteveld. 2017. 'Exploring Emerging Design Patterns in Student-Made Climate Change Games'. *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on the Foundations of Digital Games*, August 14, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3102071.3116224>.
- Barney, Christopher. 2021. *Pattern Language for Game Design*. 1st edition. CRC Press.
- Bayley, Mark, Stephen Snow, Jason Weigel, and Neil Horrocks. 2020. 'Serious Game Design to Promote Energy Literacy Among Younger Children'. *32nd Australian Conference on Human-Computer Interaction*, December 2, 531–37. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3441000.3441047>.
- Beke, Laura op de, Joost Raessens, and Stefan Werning. 2024. 'Ecogames: An Introduction'. In *Ecogames. Playful Perspectives on the Climate Crisis*, edited by Laura op de Beke, Joost Raessens, Stefan Werning, and Gerald Farca. Amsterdam University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9789048557219-001>.
- Beke, Laura op de, Joost Raessens, Stefan Werning, and Gerald Farca, eds. 2024. *Ecogames. Playful Perspectives on the Climate Crisis*. Amsterdam University Press.
- Bjork, Staffan, Jussi Holopainen, and Sus Lundgren. 2003. 'Game Design Patterns'. In *Level Up: Digital Games Research*, edited by Joost Raessens and Marinka Copier. Utrecht University.
- Breuer, Henning, and Kiril Ivanov. 2026. 'Gamification Design Patterns to Address Values-Based and Sustainability-Oriented Innovation Challenges'. *Creativity and Innovation Management* 35 (1): 154–76. <https://doi.org/10.1111/caim.70024>.
- Bunker, Lachlan, Reza Ryan, and Justin Carter. 2017. 'Combining Cooperative Design Patterns to Improve Player Experience'. *Proceedings of CreateWorld 2017*, 1–7. <https://research.usc.edu.au/esploro/outputs/conferencePaper/Combining-Cooperative-Design-Patterns-to-Improve/99472706602621>.
- Clarke, Rachel Ivy, Jin Ha Lee, and Neils Clark. 2015. 'Why Video Game Genres Fail: A Classificatory Analysis'. *Games and Culture* 12 (5): 445–65. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1555412015591900>.
- Dormann, Claire, Jennifer R. Whitson, and Max Neuvians. 2013. 'Once More With Feeling: Game Design Patterns for Learning in the Affective Domain'. *Games and Culture* 8 (4): 215–37. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1555412013496892>.
- Eriksson, Eva, Gökçe Elif Baykal, Staffan Björk, and Olof Torgersson. 2019. 'Using Gameplay Design Patterns with Children in the Redesign of a Collaborative Co-Located Game'. *Proceedings of the 18th ACM International Conference on Interaction Design and Children*, June 12, 15–25. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3311927.3323155>.
- Hajer, Maarten A., and Jeroen Oomen. 2025. *Captured Futures: Rethinking the Drama of Environmental Politics*. Oxford Scholarship Online Political Science. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/9780198955382.001.0001>.

- Hansen, Stig Børsen. 2024. 'Christopher Alexander on Design Patterns and Principles.' In *Creating Design Knowledge in Educational Innovation: Theory, Methods, and Practice*, edited by Inger-Marie F. Christensen, Lina Markauskaite, Nina Bonderup Dohn, Dwayne Ripley, and Roland Hachmann. Routledge.
- Hunicke, Robin, Marc LeBlanc, and Robert Zubek. 2004. 'MDA: A Formal Approach to Game Design and Game Research'. *Proceedings of the AAAI Workshop on Workshop on Challenges in Game AI*. <https://doi.org/10.1.1.79.4561>.
- Light, Andrew. 2000. 'What Is an Ecological Identity?' *Environmental Politics* 9 (4): 59–81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09644010008414551>.
- Lockton, Dan, David Harrison, and Neville A. Stanton. 2013. 'Exploring Design Patterns for Sustainable Behaviour'. *Design Journal* 16 (4): 431–59. <https://doi.org/10.2752/175630613X13746645186124>.
- McBride, Brooke Baldauf, Carol A. Brewer, A. R. Berkowitz, and William T. Borrie. 2013. 'Environmental Literacy, Ecological Literacy, Ecoliteracy: What Do We Mean and How Did We Get Here?' *Ecosphere* 4 (5): 1–20.
- Mitchell, Alex, Tiffany Neo, and Yui Sim. 2024. 'Patterns for Designing Poetic Gameplay'. Paper presented at Abstract Proceedings of DiGRA 2024 Conference: Playgrounds. September 30. <https://doi.org/10.26503/dl.v2024i2.2286>.
- Paeßens, Jessica, and Esther Winther. 2021. 'Game Design in Financial Literacy: Exploring Design Patterns for a Collaborative and Inclusive Serious Game from Different Perspectives'. In *Game-Based Learning Across the Disciplines*, edited by Carmela Aprea and Dirk Ifenthaler. Advances in Game-Based Learning. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75142-5_3.
- Pihkala, Panu. 2022. 'Toward a Taxonomy of Climate Emotions'. *Frontiers in Climate* 3 (January). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2021.738154>.
- Reuter, Christian, Viktor Wendel, Stefan Göbel, and Ralf Steinmetz. 2014. 'Game Design Patterns for Collaborative Player Interactions'. *Proceedings of DiGRA 2014 Conference*.
- Seymour, Nicole. 2018. *Bad Environmentalism: Irony and Irreverence in the Ecological Age*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Werning, Stefan. 2020. 'Making Data Playable – Exploring the Impact of Playfulness and Game Co-Creation on Creative Data Literacy'. *Journal of Media Literacy Education* 12 (3): 88–101.
- Whittle, Clayton, Trevin York, Paula Angela Escudra, et al. 2022. 'The Environmental Game Design Playbook (Presented by the IGDA Climate Special Interest Group)'. In *International Game Developers Association*. April. <https://igda.org/resources-archive/environmental-game-design-playbook-presented-by-igda-climate-special-interest-group-alpha-release/>.
- Widdicks, Kelly, Daniel Pargman, and Staffan Bjork. 2020. 'Backfiring and Favouring: How Design Processes in HCI Lead to Anti-Patterns and Repentant Designers'. *Proceedings of the 11th Nordic Conference on Human-Computer Interaction: Shaping Experiences, Shaping Society*, October, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3419249.3420175>.